

TOWARDS ENGINEERING SMART ECO-PACKAGING FROM FOOD SYSTEM WASTE

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Abstract: *Our study investigates the development of smart, sustainable food packaging materials derived from agricultural and household food waste. This includes, the production of bacterial cellulose from food waste-based culture media and resulting nanocrystal (BCN) used in packing formulations, the production of composite filaments of polylactic acid, BCN and graphene for smart 3D printed packaging and active packaging films made from starch extracted cassava peels and loaded with plant extracts.*